
Finding patterns in the internet's highest rated movies

A Data Management Plan created using DMPonline

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Project abstract:

IMDB (<https://www.imdb.com/>) is a popular platform for people to discover new movies and tv shows, as well as to rate ones they have already seen. They list the highest rated movies on the Top 250 page (<https://www.imdb.com/chart/top>), which thus is an easy way to explore movies that a lot of people really liked. What we are trying to do in this experiment is to find patterns in these 250 movies, we would not go as far as call it "recipes" for popular movies, but that is sort of what we are trying to find. While we are pretty sure that such recipes do not exist, otherwise Hollywood filmmakers would have probably found them by now, we do think that there is useful information hiding in this particular list. Concrete questions we are trying to answer are: are there actresses*actors that frequently appear in high rated movies? Are certain genres more popular than others? Does a certain timeframe have a higher density of highly rated movies? It is noteworthy that we took the data from a publicly accessible dataset (<https://www.kaggle.com/bartius/imdb-top-250-movies-info/data>) created by Nigel Cox (<https://www.kaggle.com/bartius>) on January 5th, 2019. While we could have scraped the data ourself, we instead checked it against the current Top 250 list and came to the conclusion that the list stayed almost identical, thus we did not see the need to collect the data once again (also the assignment states that we have to use data from an external source).

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Finding patterns in the internet's highest rated movies - Detailed DMP

1. Data summary

State the purpose of the data collection/generation

The purpose of this experiment is to find out whether or not certain "patterns" can be found in popular movies. Maybe there are certain decades that produced a much higher number of popular movies than others, maybe certain actresses*actors are featured more frequently than others. Are there certain genres which are more popular than the rest?

This data could not only be useful for film studios, but also for TV broadcasters or streaming services.

Explain the relation to the objectives of the project

Since the objective is to find out whether or not certain formulae for popular movies can be extracted, taking a look at popular movies, in our case a top 250 list of one of the biggest, if not the biggest, online platform for movie ratings, and analyzing certain distributions in said list should be, at least, a good start.

Specify the types and formats of data generated/collected

The dataset was available in .csv format, containing the top 250 movies described in 11 columns each. While some values were given as character sequences (title, rating, director, release_date), others were represented as integers (index, budget, runtime, cum_worldwide_gross), some even were comma separated lists (genre, cast) and finally the ranking was a floating point number between one and ten. It is also noteworthy that, while it technically was represented as a string, the release_date column obviously represented an actual date.

Specify if existing data is being re-used (if any)

The data is IMDB's top 250 list of highest rated movies, or more specifically a snapshot thereof created in January of 2019.

Specify the origin of the data

The data was scraped from IMDB's top 250 website (<https://www.imdb.com/chart/top>) in January 2019 and was made publicly available on kaggle (<https://www.kaggle.com/bartius/imdb-top-250-movies-info/data>) by a user named Nigel Cox (<https://www.kaggle.com/bartius>).

State the expected size of the data (if known)

The dataset contains 250 rows with 11 columns each, although not all fields have values associated (the rating column often misses values for example).

Outline the data utility: to whom will it be useful

While one of course cannot guarantee that the results are actually helpful, in theory the outcome of this experiment could be useful to movie studios (which could plan their upcoming movies according to criteria that was appearing frequently in the list) or to TV broadcasters and streaming services (who of course could pick their lineup accordingly).

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata [FAIR data]

Outline the discoverability of data (metadata provision)

Metadata can be read from the documentation/metadata.xml file within the repository available at the following DOI: <https://zenodo.org/badge/latestdoi/251582525>.

Outline the identifiability of data and refer to standard identification mechanism. Do you make use of persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers?

Yes, the repository containing the final plots, as well as the source code to reproduce them, is made available at <https://zenodo.org/badge/latestdoi/251582525>.

Outline naming conventions used

We tried to make the use of sophisticated naming conventions obsolete since we 1. "only" needed a few files to actually create the plots and 2. tried to use a clear directory structure within the repository. While we know that one does not rule out the other, we think that it certainly was sufficient for this experiment.

Outline the approach towards search keyword

We neglected search keywords as a whole, which is excusable (at least in our opinion), since this is a university assignment after all. In practise this could not have been skipped.

Outline the approach for clear versioning

While we were, in theory, trying to apply semantic versioning, it did not really work out. We think this is because of two reasons: firstly the project was of very small size, knowing when a v1.0 was ready was pretty hard since the first draft almost was a finished product. Secondly, since we did not add a v1.0 our project, in theory, still is in beta, which we do not think is the case, since the experiment itself is done. This could have been improved for sure.

Specify standards for metadata creation (if any). If there are no standards in your discipline describe what metadata will be created and how

Our metadata file was created using the Dublin Core standard for metadata https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Dublin_Core.

2.2 Making data openly accessible [FAIR data]

Specify which data will be made openly available? If some data is kept closed provide rationale for doing so

Any data produced (or reproducible by running the scripts) is made openly available, indefinitely.

Specify how the data will be made available

The data, in particular the plots and the source code, have already been made available on a GitHub repository <https://github.com/matthiasweiss/dsue1-2020s>.

Specify what methods or software tools are needed to access the data? Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included? Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

To access (=download) the data/code one either needs a web browser or any other program to fetch contents from servers (e.g. wget). To reproduce the results, in this case re-drawing the plots, changing parameters, etc., Python (<https://www.python.org/>) 3.7 is necessary.

Specify where the data and associated metadata, documentation and code are deposited

As stated before, the plots and the source code are already available on a GitHub repository <https://github.com/matthiasweiss/dsue1-2020s>.

Specify how access will be provided in case there are any restrictions

If GitHub for whatever reason removes the repository we will try to host it on a different service as soon as possible.

2.3 Making data interoperable [FAIR data]

Assess the interoperability of your data. Specify what data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies you will follow to facilitate interoperability.

The raw dataset is stored as a .csv file, the results for the plots can be extracted from the source files by exporting the respective python dictionaries to whatever format one likes. Since python itself is open source there are really no restrictions here.

Specify whether you will be using standard vocabulary for all data types present in your data set, to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability? If not, will you provide mapping to more commonly used ontologies?

The dataset only makes use of strings, integers, floating point numbers, dates and comma separated lists. We would assume these to be standard vocabulary.

2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses) [FAIR data]

Specify how the data will be licenced to permit the widest reuse possible

The data as well as the source code are licensed under the CC0-license (<https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/>) as stated in the LICENSE.md file in the repository.

Specify when the data will be made available for re-use. If applicable, specify why and for what period a data embargo is needed

Neither the data nor the source code is associated with an embargo.

Specify whether the data produced and/or used in the project is useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why

The data, as well as the source code, is freely usable by anyone who likes to use it, indefinitely.

Describe data quality assurance processes

Due to time constraints there were no sophisticated data quality assurance processes, in a "real-world" project this must have been the case.

Specify the length of time for which the data will remain re-usable

The data will remain re-usable indefinitely, or at least until this university lecture (Data Stewardship UE, 2020S) is over.

3. Allocation of resources

Estimate the costs for making your data FAIR. Describe how you intend to cover these costs

Besides the compensation for the working hours, which effectively is zero due to this being a university assignment, there are no additional costs for making the data FAIR.

Clearly identify responsibilities for data management in your project

Due to the small size and tight time constraints the data management responsibilities really only were the original exploration of possible datasets and the transformation using the couple scripts we wrote.

Describe costs and potential value of long term preservation

The only costs which could appear in the long term are if either GitHub or Zenodo will not be free in the future anymore, which we rate as highly unlikely.

4. Data security

Address data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data

While we consider GitHub a secure storage, since a large proportion of the internet relies on its services, at least a secondary backup would be favorable. Due to the fact that we do not transfer sensitive data, it is not necessary to discuss this part.

5. Ethical aspects

To be covered in the context of the ethics review, ethics section of DoA and ethics deliverables. Include references and related technical aspects if not covered by the former

Since we provided all our results (including source code) under the CC0 license, there should be no legal or ethical issues. Solely the fact that our experiment may be a little bit biased due to the fact, that we only used one platform to gather our data from could (maybe) be considered "unethical", but we do not think so.

6. Other

Refer to other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management that you are using (if any)

We do not have any other procedures for data management in place.